

Foreign Language Learning and Verbal Competence

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses approaches to the features of the formation of verbal competencies in English classes. The problem of changing approaches to the formation of a system of key competencies that allow you to effectively apply the acquired knowledge in a practical situation and successfully use it in the process of social adaptation has always translated its indisputable relevance. The authors of the article are convinced that verbal competencies, which form the core of students' oratory, are necessary for future professional activities.

Key words: *Competence, verbal competencies, professional activities, knowledge.*

INTRODUCTION

Competence is a set of knowledge, skills, abilities and personal qualities that allow participants to develop speech activities aimed at specific learning goals.

The communicative competence of a foreign language is the ability and readiness to communicate with native speakers, as well as the ability of students to get acquainted with the culture of the country in which the language is studied, to better understand the culture of their country, to present it in communication. holds. The main objectives of studying this subject include the development of the following competencies in students:

Linguistic competence implies sufficient knowledge of language materials (phonetics, vocabulary, grammar) and the ability to use them in various speech activities (listening, speaking, reading and writing) to communicate with students.

In modern linguistics, the problem of communication is being developed. One of the results here is the concept of communicative competence, defined as “possession of complex communication skills and abilities, the formation of adequate skills in new social structures, knowledge of cultural norms and restrictions in communication, knowledge of customs, traditions, etiquette in the field of communication, observance of decency, good breeding; orientation in communication means inherent in the national, class mentality, mastering the role repertoire within the framework of this profession” [2]. It is possible to isolate its components - verbal competence and non-verbal (socio-cultural) competence. Verbal competence is defined as the appropriateness of statements, taking into account the context and subtext of the statement, the absence of difficulties in written and oral speech, the variability in the interpretation of information, good orientation in the field of evaluative stereotypes and patterns, the plurality of meanings of the concepts used, the metaphorical nature of speech. Competence in this case characterizes the subject of communication, its subjective qualities.

An example of verbal competence is the activity of a professional translator who simultaneously translates oral speech. In this case, he is required to quickly and adequately understand the statement, find and use the exact equivalent in the literal and contextual meaning of words and concepts. The opposite example, that is, an example of verbal incompetence, can be the inappropriate use of proverbs, sayings, speech stamps, professionalism in a new or inappropriate social context. The source of problems in the perception of a foreign language culture can be sociolinguistic interference, i.e. the use of the rules of speech communication of

representatives of one language culture in communication with a representative of another language culture. This occurs when a foreign language is spoken using native language communication patterns, such as expressing and responding to a compliment.

A stereotype of speech behavior or a stereotype of communication associated with a picture of the world, an ordered culture, its values, helps a person to live in a complex social reality.

DISCUSSIONS

Verbal communication, using language and speech as tools, has long been a subject of interest for many researchers. Speech as the highest mental function is one of the components of intellectual activity, and language as the main means of speech activity and the implementation of thought processes are in the focus of such sciences as psychology, linguistics, psycholinguistics, neurolinguistics, sociology, cultural studies, political science and many other sciences.

Verbal communication concerns all areas of human conscious activity. Man is social by nature. He can live harmoniously and act only in the environment of other people, with whom he enters into social structures and performs public functions. Each person is a personality that manifests itself through social roles - in marriage, in the family, at work, in school, on vacation, etc. The inclusion of an individual in the structure of society is a motive that encourages children to learn their native language, and adults to learn a foreign language. Socialization is achieved through communication. Communication is based on mutual understanding and interaction and on a powerful motive - the need for socialization.

In the scientific literature, there are different options for defining communication between people. In the psychological literature, communication is

defined as “the process of exchanging thoughts, information and emotional experiences between people” [8]. The terms "communication" and "communication" are often considered as close concepts, but they are not synonymous. Communication stands out as part of the structure of communication, along with interaction, understood as the organization of interaction and impact, and perception, as sensory perception. Communication here acts as an exchange of information. In English literature, the term "communication" means the exchange of thoughts and information in the form of speech or written signals, which is synonymous with the concept of "communication" [3].

The word communication comes from the Latin "communico", "communicare" and means unity, conversation [2]. The Latin word "communicatio" includes such concepts as communication, conversation [2]. Based on the Latin form of the term "communication", we can conclude that the concepts of "communication" and "communication" can be used as synonyms or interchangeable words. The difference in the description of these terms is associated with particular features of the disclosure of communication processes in various sciences.

Together with the concept of “verbal communication”, the term “interpersonal communication” is often used, since communication with the help of words is a fundamental feature of human communication and implies a personal or personal nature of communication. The term "verbal" comes from the Latin "verbum" - the word [4]. In the psychological dictionary, verbal communication is defined as “a purposeful process of transferring some mental content with the help of language (language code)” [5]. Verbal communication is communication with words and speech. This is the process of information exchange and emotional interaction between people or groups using speech tools. Verbal communication is a complex

information-sign system in which individual, social, cultural components interact. The personality carries out verbal activity as a purposeful act. The ability to manage the process of verbal communication is an important competence that determines the success of a person in society [8].

Verbal communication is carried out as a process of creating, sending, interpreting messages by means of language and speech. It is woven into the process of interpersonal communication, which has a complex dynamic character. Verbal communication is a complex of joint activities of interlocutors. The main means of verbal communication are language and speech, which ensure the exchange of information between individuals. “Language serves communication and can be called a communicative process in its purest form... Without language, any form of communication becomes impossible” [3]. Linguistic, verbal communication is the creation, exchange and interpretation of messages by communicants using language as a code in order to achieve changes in the behavior or consciousness of the addresser necessary for joint activities [4].

Every nation, every culture has its own language system, the so-called system of language codes, which serves as a verbal tool for communication in a given society. Languages of different cultures have their own characteristics, their own codes. In order for the language to be convenient for communication, each language has typical stereotypes with the help of which people of the same language culture designate what is common for understanding. Communicative influence in the process of verbal communication can be carried out when the communicants have the same or similar coding or decoding systems. In other words, for mutual understanding, the interlocutors must speak the same language.

At the heart of acts of communication is the reflection of the surrounding reality by a person. Language, as a means of verbal coding, displays the world

around in the human mind. According to the Sapir-Whorf hypothesis, language is the basis of the picture of the world that each person develops and puts in order a huge number of objects and phenomena observed by a person in the world around him. The object and phenomenon become available only when they are given a name. The word does not reflect the object or phenomenon of the surrounding world itself, but how a person sees it through the prism of one or another picture of the world, perceived through the experience of previous generations, through communication with other people [4].

Functional literacy involves mastering a system of key competencies that allow you to effectively apply the acquired knowledge in a practical situation and successfully use them in the process of social adaptation. One of the most important key competencies is the ability to work with information, with text. Life in our rapidly changing world imposes a number of new requirements on reading, for the satisfaction of which a very wide range of tasks must be solved. In the process of teaching the foreign language, it is very important to understand that one of the priority tasks of the work is the technology of forming new neural connections, which will allow the teacher to learn how to recreate his own experience with his students. After reviewing and analyzing the results of the entrance test, the teacher begins to think about how to design assignments and exercises in order to form verbal competencies and communication skills, initiate real changes and involve students in an interesting learning process [5].

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, I would like to emphasize that the variety of concepts of the educational process that has developed in modern pedagogical theory will remain far from complete if the problems of communicative competence and the importance of live dialogue are underestimated.

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